

C3MR LNG PROCESS OPTIMIZATION: PARALLEL GENETIC ALGORITHM INTERFACE

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Abstract

Environmental protection and sustainable development, emissions, energy efficiency, and economic profits have become important considerations in the present industrial studies. These considerations are now being simultaneously included as multiple optimization objectives. To this day, the non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm (NSGA-II) is the most widely utilized multi-objective optimization algorithm in real-world applications. A significant effort has been made to connect the NSGA-II algorithm with modern process simulators such as Aspen Plus. However, Aspen Plus-based genetic optimization suffers from extensive computation time. To tackle this problem, a novel approach, the Parallel Genetic Algorithm Interface, is proposed. As opposed to the traditional approach, the PAGAN algorithm makes use of the fact that fitness functions can be vectorized in Matlab-based GA, and that Aspen Plus simulations can be run asynchronously. Thanks to the accelerated algorithm, extensive optimization studies were made possible. For our studies, the propane-precooled mixed-refrigerant (C3MR) liquefaction process was chosen. A standard C3MR 3.5 MTPA LNG production process scheme was set up in Aspen Plus environment with 18 process parameters selected for single- and dual-objective optimization of both the processing costs and the associated CO₂ emissions, with the process parameter deviation range of $\pm 75\%$. The PAGAN algorithm achieved a seven-fold decrease in the computation time which enabled increasing the number of individuals in the optimization runs up to 1000, while achieving a 12% decrease in processing costs and 14% decrease in CO₂ emissions. The difference in the Pareto front position between the runs led to the conclusion that the number of individuals needed to approach the optimal conditions in C3MR LNG production is much higher than the 200 commonly used in studies.

Introduction

Real-world multi-objective optimization problems include several criteria that need to be optimized simultaneously while the objective functions are often conflicting. The process parameters may often be imprecise, and the objective functions may have many extremes. Therefore, the process of multi-objective optimization is very exhausting and traditional methods usually fail when trying to solve such problems¹.

Nowadays, the most widely utilized optimization methods are modern stochastic methods and namely genetic algorithms and their variations. These algorithms are very robust, they do not break easily, and they are good for solving multi-modal and multi-dimensional problems. Moreover, the multi-objective non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm² (NSGA-II) has been directly included in the Matlab Optimization toolbox since 2007 and is thus a ready-to-use algorithm.

This work aims for improvement of a multi-objective optimization interface providing broadened possibilities of optimization of Aspen Plus-based process simulations. The object of study was the APCI C3MR LNG process closer explained in conference paper "C3MR LNG Process Optimization: Enviro-economic study" presented at the ICCT 2022 conference.

Methodology: Parallel Genetic Algorithm Interface

Genetic algorithm is a global optimization method derived from evolution and natural selection. And nature follows an interesting path to select an optimum solution to any problem. By generations, nature chooses and keeps the best and fittest individuals which it lets to reproduce, and it discards the rest. In this work, two objective functions were evaluated: levelized processing costs and carbon dioxide emissions, both associated with production of LNG via propane-precooled mixed-refrigerant (C3MR) process. For optimization, 18 process variables were altered. From the algorithm's point of view, these variables create the genome of an individual, i.e., one individual consists of a random combination of values of these 18 parameters. The algorithm creates a population, which is a series of combinations of the parameter values. For each individual, a simulation of the process is carried out in Aspen Plus software. Based on the objective function values, the algorithm chooses the best individuals which are those with the lowest values of the objective functions and applies no changes to these individuals. In the nature, if the evolution is slow, random changes may occur to genes. The algorithm

therefore finds the weakest individuals and applies random changes to them for a chance to randomly create something better. For the rest of the individuals, the algorithm combines their genes to create potentially stronger individuals. This way a whole new population is obtained which is potentially better than the previous one. The algorithm then ranks the new generation, chooses the best, the worst, and repeats the entire process. This procedure is repeated until the population cannot be more improved. In this work, 1000 individuals were used, and the cycle was repeated 500 times.

To link the genetic algorithm with Aspen Plus software, the ActiveX technology was used. It is a technology developed by Microsoft for sharing information across various platforms and it provides virtually unlimited control over selected software. It is compatible with Matlab and enables the user to gain almost unlimited control over practically any simulation software, for example Aspen HYSYS, Aspen Plus, gPROMS, PRO/II and so forth. When working with Aspen Plus, this technology enables the user to write a code that can run simulations, alter the settings, read and write data, etc.

An obvious problem with the Aspen-linked genetic-algorithm optimization is that the simulation needs to be run for each individual in each generation, i.e., in this case $1000 \times 500 = 5 \times 10^5$ simulations need to be run. Considering just one second per simulation this results in a computation time of 5×10^5 seconds or 5.8 days.

To solve this common recurring problem with optimization using Aspen Plus, a novel optimization interface dubbed the Parallel Genetic Algorithm Interface or PAGAN³ was proposed. This interface makes use of two aspects:

1. In Matlab-based GA the objective function can be called on the entire population at once⁴.
2. Any number of Aspen Plus simulations can be running simultaneously, provided that they have a different name, and they can be run asynchronously, i.e., the algorithm does not wait for a running simulation to finish and continues to the next step⁵.

The traditional genetic algorithm creates the population and sends individuals one by one into just one simulation. To evaluate G individuals, the algorithm needs G cycles. On the other hand, PAGAN creates copies of the original simulation. If the number of copies is N, the number of necessary cycles is G/N as shown in Figure 1. Detailed layout of this algorithm is displayed in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Comparison of standard and proposed algorithm

Results and discussion

Performance of the proposed interface was evaluated using a desktop computer with an AMD Ryzen 9 3900X 3.80 GHz 12-core processor and a 48 GB RAM. Several test runs were executed, each with a different number of simultaneous simulations (N). To avoid unnecessarily extensive computation times during the performance test, the population was reduced to 100 individuals and 50 generations were generated. To guarantee reproducibility, each test run was initiated with identical initial population. Absolute computation times are shown in Figure 3. A great reduction in computation time can be observed with increasing number of simultaneous simulations. In Figure 3, the relative computation rate is the ratio of computation time using one simulation to the computation time using the respective number of simultaneous simulations. The trend is linear up to $N = 4$ and then gradually flattens. Nonetheless, a relative computation rate of approximately 7.5 was achieved with 24 simultaneous simulations. This, however, is strongly dependent on the performance of the processor and the capacity of the RAM.

Figure 2. PAGAN algorithm for NSGA-II optimization.

Figure 3. Absolute computation time and relative computation rate for various numbers of simultaneous simulations

As a direct consequence of the 750% increase in computation speed, sequential dual-objective optimization of the C3MR LNG process was made possible. The optimization procedure was initiated with a population of 200 individuals over 200 generations. The results of the first run were used as the initial population for the second run. This was repeated in eight runs, hence the term sequential optimization. The number of individuals was gradually increased to final number of 1000 individuals. In the eighth run, optimization boundaries regarding the two objective functions were found and later confirmed by two single-objective optimization runs. From Figure 4 it is evident how the optimization progressed throughout the individual runs. This underlines the need for repeated optimization. A 10-12% decrease in processing costs and a 13-14% decrease in carbon dioxide emissions were achieved.

Figure 4. Single- and dual-objective optimization results (Number of individuals displayed in parentheses.)

In addition to dual-objective optimization of the C3MR process, the in-optimization behavior of parameters was studied. First, evolution of parameters was analyzed. Average values of each of the parameters in individual runs is displayed in Figure 5. The evolution of parameters shows how much the process parameters changed between individual runs. Moreover, the evolution is a direct indicator of the optimization results' quality – the more parameters remain unchanged between runs (or change slightly), the closer to the global optimum the optimization is. Based on the parameters' evolution, one can see which parameters cause the initial decrease in the objective function values (e.g., P_{K201}) and which affect the last runs (e.g., P_{TV202}).

Figure 5. Evolution of process parameters throughout optimization runs.

Secondly, the interest was focused on the parameter variance which defines the shape of the Pareto front. The parameter ranges (or the ratios of maximal-to-minimal values) for each of the optimization runs were calculated and displayed in Figure 6. Some parameters, such as P_{K202} reported almost identical values throughout the optimization process. Hence, these parameters affect the shape of the Pareto front minimally. This implies that certain values of these parameters can satisfy both objective functions simultaneously. On the contrary, parameters such as P_{TV104} were reported in a wide range of values and, therefore, it can be deduced that such parameters cannot be optimized to a single value simultaneously satisfying both objectives.

Figure 6. Parameter variance throughout optimization runs.

Values of the most crucial parameters based on their variance were normalized and plotted against normalized values of the objective functions in Figure 7. The figure shows that the trends of function values of all parameters are well developed and that the trends regarding the two objectives are approximately inverse to each other. An exception to this is P_{TV104} which shows slightly different behavior.

Figure 7. Fuzzy-normalized relations between values of the objective functions and optimized parameters

Conclusion

The main contribution of this work lies in the development of an advanced optimization interface which achieved 750% increase in the optimization rate. However, this value is strongly dependent on the used hardware. On the other hand, with the current rate of development of information technology it can be assumed that this value will increase overtime. The sequential dual-objective optimization revealed the

behavior of the process parameters and optimization boundaries. In the end, it has been proven that, by selecting the crucial parameters, an even more effective optimization can be done.

Acknowledgement

This study was supported by the Slovak Research and Development Agency under contract nos. APVV-18-0134 and APVV-19-0170, and by the Slovak Scientific Agency, grant no. VEGA 1/0511/21.

References

1. Cui Y., Geng Z., Zhu Q., Han Y. *Energy*. 125, 681 (2017)
2. Deb K., Pratap A., Agarwal S., Meyarivan T. *IEEE Trans. Evol. Comput.* 6, 182 (2002).
3. Furda P., Variny M., Labovská Z. *Energy Convers. Manag.* 260, 115602 (2022).
4. Aspen Technology, Inc.: *Aspen Plus User Guide*, Version V10.2.
5. The MathWorks, Inc.: *Genetic Algorithm Options*, 2021. <https://uk.mathworks.com/help/gads/genetic-algorithm-options.html#f17234> (accessed: 21. 2. 2022)